

LuftBlick Report 2023007

About Pandora Lunar Measurements

Final Report QA4EO WP2322

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1 Document Change Record

Issue	Date	Section	Observations
1	30 Apr 2023	All	First version

2 Summary and Conclusions

3 Introduction, Summary and Conclusions

This is the final report of work package (WP) 2322 “Night-time aerosol and trace gasses columnar observations” of the ESA project [QA4EO](#) phase2¹ for the time period 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023.

This WP had essentially three major goals, which are briefly described, summarized and concluded in the following:

Goal 1) Test the impact of difference reference spectra used

This first goal is splitted into two parts. First, the impact of a lunar albedo correction model has been investigated. Although the lunar light is reflected sun-light, a spectral difference to a solar spectra due to a non-uniform spectral albedo is intrinsic. Since the current reference spectra is taken from solar measurements, the impact of this correction should be quantified. The study revealed an impact by using the spectral lunar albedo correction model for high lunar phases up to 8%. This impact is not negligible and will therefore be incorporated in the [Blick Software Suite \(BSS\)](#) for further evaluation. However, the smooth spectral structure of the albedo is rather well captured by the correction polynomials in the retrievals.

The impact of the lunar albedo correction is rather small and can therefore not explain the strong difference we encounter when a reference spectrum is either compiled from solar or lunar spectra. Since the solar measurements are taken with diffusers, and the lunar measurements without a diffuser, this might point to an incomplete or improper filter characterization. Unfortunately, the reason for that could not yet be determined.

¹ Quality Assurance for Earth Observation project [Statement of Work for LuftBlick], SERCO Contract QA4EO/SER/SUB/04, 2022.

Goal 2) Fine-tune the spectral fitting setup for lunar retrievals

The goal of this task was to settle the spectral fitting setup, and incorporate the findings into the [BSS](#). Based on prototype fitting setups from the previous QA4EO, the fine-tuning focused on improvements on the challenging period of the solar twilight. Therefore a Ring correction has been included in the retrieval setting and tested. This Ring effect relates to inelastic scattering processes in diffuse skylight which can cause a broadening of the spectral lines in the measurements. The findings reveal an impact of up to 10 % if the Ring-spectrum correction is included in the spectral fitting.

Goal 3) Obtain optimized quality indicators

The retrieval products using the latest calibration procedure (goal 1), and fitting setup (goal 2), is used to derive quality flagging criteria which allows a simple data usage for users. Based on a fine-tuned quality indicator and two more guidelines on how to use the lunar data, the retrieval products can be used with high confidence. In particular, lunar ozone total columns should be averaged by 1 hour, and all data products have to be filtered in terms of the sun's solar zenith angle ([SZA](#)). This is related to the open task of goal 2), where shortly before sunrise, diffuse sunlight already impacts the lunar measurements.

3.1 Acronyms and Abbreviations

AMF	Air mass factor
BSS	Blick Software Suite
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
DOAS	Differential optical absorption spectroscopy
H ₂ O	Water vapor
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
NO ₃	Nitrate radical
O ₃	Ozone
QA4EO	Quality Assurance for Earth Observation

QI	Quality indicator
QIT	Quality indicator threshold
ROLO	RObotic Lunar Observatory
SZA	Solar zenith angle
WP	Work package
wrms	Normalized rms of fitting residuals weighted with independent uncertainty

4 Reference spectra

The [DOAS](#)-like spectral fitting approach as implemented in the [BSS](#) uses an absorption-free reference spectra created from Pandora measurements. The ideal scenario would be to pick a reference from Pandora lunar measurements, estimate the gas slant column amounts to make it absorption-free, and use this one in the spectral fitting. Although the lunar light is reflected sunlight, the brightness of the lunar disc changes in a complex, but smooth way. With the inclusion of several closure polynomials in the minimization of the spectral fitting, the hypothesis is that one could even use a solar spectra for lunar retrievals, as the closure polynomials compensate for the smooth lunar spectral albedo. The lunar albedo ([Figure LunarAlbedo](#)), as retrieved from several sensors, shows such a rather smooth spectral dependency, which supports this assumption to use a solar spectra right away. Therefore, these two scenarios are compared in the following .

Figure LunarAlbedo: Lunar albedo retrieved from several sensors as described in [Dobber](#).

4.1 Solar versus Lunar reference Spectra

The first approach for lunar retrievals make use of a reference spectra which is made from solar measurements. To create a proper reference spectra from lunar measurements can be cumbersome due to the low signal input during lunar measurements. This results in a larger independent uncertainty (~ measurement noise). Further, clear sky periods during lunar measurements can be

short, which can make it difficult to obtain the correct gas amount in this reference in order to make it absorption-free. This larger uncertainty is also propagated to the normalized averaged spectral fitting residuals, where direct sun retrievals (black dots in [Figure NO₂WRMS](#)) are about 1 decade lower than lunar retrievals (yellow and green dots in [Figure NO₂WRMS](#)). However, this enhanced wrms is related to the independent uncertainty, and is not affecting the point-to-point variation in the final NO₂ dataproduct ([Figure LunarNO₂](#)), in particular around full-moon-periods and clear sky conditions.

Figure NO₂WRMS: NO₂ retrieval wrms for Pandora 138 spectrometer 2 at Rome Sapienza for lunar (yellow, green) and direct sun retrievals (black).

The NO₂ example of Pandora 138 at Rome Sapienza illustrates how the lunar retrievals (blue dots in [Figure LunarNO₂](#)) are apparently closing the gap between the direct sun measurements (red dots in [Figure LunarNO₂](#)). In this example, the first and last two days are related to slightly overcast conditions, which causes more independent uncertainty that is also visible in the enhanced [wrms](#) for those periods.

The use of a lunar reference spectra (yellow dots in [Figure NO₂WRMS](#)), leads to a slightly higher wrms for lunar retrievals, compared to the ones using a solar reference (green dots in [Figure NO₂WRMS](#)).

Notably, this NO_2 dataproduct leads to a significantly lower total NO_2 amount (green dots in [Figure LunarNO₂](#)), when the lunar reference spectra is applied. However, when comparing those two curves, the green one indicates a more consistent transition to the direct sun data, and there is only an AMF-dependent difference. Therefore, if one would use a smaller slant column amount for making the solar reference absorption-free, one can bring the blue curve on top of the green one. This means that the usage of one or the other spectra can lead to the same total NO_2 , but is only dependent on the estimated slant column amount in the reference. To obtain the proper slant column amount in the solar reference, the MLE-approach is used during the calibration using solar measurement. When using the same approach by taking only lunar measurements for the MLE (but a reference from solar spectra), the more meaningful smaller slant column amount is obtained. Consequently, a feasible way to retrieve lunar columns would be to use either a second reference spectrum from lunar measurements, or use a second calibration factor for lunar measurements and stick to the solar reference spectrum. Either way is inconvenient for the current software and would require a major software upgrade. Instead we try to get to the bottom of this unexpected discrepancy. It either indicates

- A. that the assumption of the lunar albedo impact being absorbed by the closure polynomials of the fitting algorithm does not hold true. In this case the lunar correction model would be needed.
- B. or that improper instrument characterization does not sufficiently address the differences in the filters utilized to produce the solar reference spectrum and the lunar measurements or any other instrumental effect that comes into play here. Note that direct sun measurements use a diffuser, but lunar measurements do not for signal to noise reasons.

Ad A.:

We can already see from figure [LunarNO₂](#) that applying a lunar albedo correction prior to the spectral fitting does not change the overall picture (purple dots). Details about this implementation can be found in section [4.2 Lunar Albedo Correction](#).

Ad B.:

Several tests have been carried out already to identify the root of this bias, but it could not be isolated yet. Revealing this shortcoming is key, not only for lunar retrievals but for all retrievals where the reference spectrum and the measurements use different filter settings.

Figure LunarNO₂: Direct total NO₂ for Pandora 138 spectrometer 2 at Rome Sapienza for Lunar (green,blue,magenta) and direct sun retrievals (red).

4.2 Lunar Albedo Correction

We followed the approach from [Kiefer and Stone](#) who developed a parameterized model of the lunar spectral albedo from observations carried out by the RObotic Lunar Observatory ([ROLO](#)). The model makes use of several astronomical parameters that can be calculated from the SPICE observation geometry information system (e.g. [Acton et al.](#)), from NASA's Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility. A suitable astronomical Python library, including the harvesting of SPICE datasets, offers the

package [Skyfield](#). An example application of the lunar spectral albedo correction close to the full moon (lunar phase ~ 0) is illustrated in Figure [ROLOApplication](#).

Figure [ROLOApplication](#): This sequence of plots (left to right) shows the correction from a lunar spectrum (left) to an apparent solar spectrum (right) using the modeled lunar spectral albedo (middle).

The minor impact on the final data has been shown already in Figure [LunarNO₂](#). The percentage change in total NO₂ upon application of the albedo correction is given in Figure [ImpactLunarAlbedoCorrection](#) as a function of lunar zenith angle (x-axis) and lunar phase (color coding). A reduction of up to about 8 % can be experienced for high lunar phases, where the lunar disc is already illuminated quite inhomogeneously. The at first sight counter intuitive dependency on the lunar zenith angle is a consequence of the not straightforward orbit of the moon around the Earth. One part is the ~ 5 degree inclination of the moon's orbit with respect to the ecliptic plane.

The implementation of the lunar correction model in the [BSS](#) would require a change in the processing logic and would be therefore not compatible with the current software version 1.8. Consequently, this software upgrade will be realized as part of the next software release version 1.9.

Figure [ImpactLunarAlbedoCorrection](#): Impact of lunar albedo correction on lunar NO₂ total column amounts.

5 Fine-tuning the spectral fitting set-up

The first fitting setups for lunar trace gas retrievals have been successfully prototyped as part of the previous QA4EO project² for NO_2 , O_3 , H_2O and NO_3 . The temporary fitting setups for those gasses can be found in the corresponding technical note ([Tiefengraber and Cede](#)). The fitting setup for NO_2 is basically the one which is used for the official direct-sun code nvs3 ([Cede et al.](#)), which has been tested extensively in another project ([Tiefengraber et al.](#)). The speciality of this fitting setup is the use of two settings which use a different NO_2 effective temperature. Based on a stratospheric NO_2 climatology, a stratospheric/tropospheric split can be calculated, which uses a more realistic effective gas temperature for the spectral fitting and effective height for the direct moon AMF-calculation.

Testing the prototype data products made clear that in particular twilight conditions are difficult to handle. This can be seen e.g. in Figure [LunarNO₂](#) or [TwilightMeasurements](#) where during twilight conditions data tend to scatter more or are even biased high. A positive bias can be explained by an underestimation of the AMF, meaning the light path is longer as expected by the direct sun AMF model due to multiple scattering.

This radiance dilution (or spatial stray light) impacts the spectrum in two connected ways. Firstly, due to the higher scattering probability in the UV, the spectrum is “tilted”. Secondly, inelastic scattering processes (as a consequence of the multiple scattering) cause an apparent line-filling (or broadening) of the spectral lines. This effect is named after the discoverer Grainger and Ring (therefore Ring-effect). The Ring-effect can be accounted for in the spectral fitting algorithm by including a pseudo Ring cross section.

The impact on the NO_2 retrieval when the Ring-effect is compensated illustrates [Figure ImpactLunarAlbedoCorrection](#). Close to full-moon (small phase angles) NO_2 columns are mainly

unaffected by the effect, but can be reduced to several percent close to moon rise (during twilight). The impact is stronger (up to about 10 %) for larger lunar phase angles and therefore could extend the observation period around full-moon.

² Quality Assurance for Earth Observation project [Annex B, Statement of Work for LuftBlick], SERCO Contract QA4EO/SER/SUB/04, 2020.

Figure ImpactRingCorrection: Impact of ring correction on lunar NO_2 total column amounts.

6 Optimized quality indicator

6.1 Spectral fitting residuals

Quality indicators (QI) serve as a decision basis, which retrievals should be used for further studies. In order to provide the user a simple decision, each measurement receives its quality flag. The flags are clustering the measurements into the three categories of high, medium, and low data quality, which is done for all the processing levels. This also means that certain thresholds have to be defined for each data product. Most of the QI are similar or even the same for different data products, especially on the level 1 site. However, on the spectral fitting side, the most important QI is the normalized rms of the spectral fitting residuals (wrms), which gives a measure how good the model agrees with the measurement. Therefore, this section will present the obtained thresholds for this parameter.

For this work package, the long-term and uninterrupted data series for Pandora 117 spectrometer 2, located at Rome-Sapienza ([Figure TwilightMeasurements](#)) has been used to derive the threshold for the wrms.

The approach ([Gebetsberger et al, Chapter 4.4.1](#)) is based on the empirical distribution of the wrms, with the assumption that two different value-clusters exist. Those clusters refer once to clear-sky conditions, when the integration time can be as low as possible with less variation during the measurement period. In the second cluster, overcast conditions are dominating and typically lead to higher exposure times with higher variability during the measurements, which also leads to an enhanced wrms. The approach is fitting a mixed Gaussian distribution to these two regimes, where the corresponding weighted cumulative distribution function (CDF) is used to derive the quality limits. The probability values of 0.9 and 0.1 to be within the clearsky cluster are then used as the QIT to separate the data quality.

The obtained CDF's are illustrated in [Figure NO₂-O₃-CDF](#) and [Figure NO₃-H₂O-CDF](#), which lead to the final wrms thresholds for each output gas as presented in [Table LimitsWRMS](#).

Figure TwilightMeasurements: Lunar total NO₂ for Pandora 117 spectrometer 2 at Rome Sapienza with the optimized quality limits. Twilight conditions are labeled as red dots.

Figure NO₂-O₃-CDF: CDF for Lunar NO₂ and O₃.

Figure NO₃-H₂O-CDF: CDF for Lunar NO₃ and H₂O.

Gas	QIT1	QIT2
H2O	9e-4	2.2e-3
NO2	2.1e-3	4.5e-3
NO3	2.4e-3	3.7e-3
O3	1.8e-3	4.2e-3

Table LimitsWRMS: Quality limits for wrms raising the quality flag from high to medium (QIT1) and from medium to low (QIT2).

6.2 Data preparation guidelines

Since the current quality flagging criteria do not sufficiently capture the twilight situation (see section [5 Fine-tuning the spectral fitting set-up](#)), all 'unwanted' data points which are obviously outliers, two additional data preparation guidelines have been derived.

As exemplarily shown in the NO₂ time series ([Figure TwilightMeasurements](#)), there are some strong outliers, indicated as red dots, which are not captured by the current quality flagging criteria. These cases mostly refer to twilight conditions, where diffuse sunlight is entering the lunar lightpath affecting the retrievals. This is also visible for other output gasses, e.g. lunar O₃ or H₂O. Although an active diffuse correction is already applied on measurements during those conditions (off-moon measurements are subtracted from on-moon measurements), this certainly has to be improved in future efforts. Therefore, an additional filtering by the SZA is currently suggested for all data products. In particular, only retrievals with SZA>95 should be used in the analysis.

The second guideline refers to lunar O_3 , which is derived from the Chappuis bands in the visible. Due to the high uncertainty of the retrievals in that spectral range, a time averaging of 1 hour is recommended.

7 Future work

Based on the outcomes of this work package, some potential future working tasks can be concluded:

- The **source of the bias** coming from different reference spectra used needs to be studied further, if it is a consequence of missing or improper instrument characterization .
- **Radiance “dilution”** corrections during solar twilight shall be studied. “Active” correction techniques, like radiance measurements recorded next to the moon and close in time, have been prototyped already, but would need further refinement. Feasibility studies towards “passive” correction techniques including modeling or aerosol proxies (like O_2O_2 columns as utilized in MAX-DOAS) would be carried out.
- Investigate the improvement capability by considering the **Raman effect** under **solar twilight conditions**. Test in particular what gasses (respectively spectral regimes) are affected most and if molecular absorption (molecular Ring effect) needs to be considered for strong absorbers (e.g. H_2O or O_3).